

EXA4MIND

D4.1

Intermediate Version of the ADAMS4SIMS System

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Abstract

The Automated Data Mining System for Systematic Improvement of Molecular Simulations (ADAMS4SIMS) is currently at an intermediate stage of development. This version of ADAMS4SIMS integrates a suite of functionalities essential for the preprocessing, storage, and analysis of molecular dynamics data. The system consists of a back-end, a web-based GUI, and a PostgreSQL database. The HDF5 format is employed for managing large trajectory datasets effectively. While the preprocessing tools focus on metadata extraction and data preparation, the analytical tools available provide users with the capability to perform analyses of their simulations. The intermediate version of ADAMS4SIMS presented with this deliverable lays the groundwork for future enhancements, with a roadmap that includes improving data accessibility, preprocessing and advancing analytical methodologies.

Keywords

Molecular Dynamics Simulations; Database systems; HDF5; Metadata extraction; Extreme Data; Research Data Management; EXA4MIND

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Dissemination Levels

PU Public Public, fully open, e.g. website

SEN Sensitive Confidential to EXA4MIND project and Commission Services

Deliverable Types

- R** Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC** Websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER** Software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

ADAMS4SIMS	Automated Data Mining System for Systematic Improvement of Molecular Simulations
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AQIS	Advanced Query and Indexing System
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CPPTRAJ	Software for Processing and Analysis of Molecular Dynamics Trajectory Data
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
ER	Entity Relationship
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (Principles for RDM, Wilkinson et al. 2016)
GPCR	G Protein Coupled Receptors
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format, version 5 (Folk et al. 2011)
HPC	High Performance Computing
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LEXIS	Large-scale EXecution for Industry & Society Platform, resulting – in its first version – from the H2020 LEXIS Project GA #825532
MD	Molecular Dynamics
MDDb	Molecular Dynamics Data Bank
NumPy	Numerical Python (Harris et al. 2020)
NVMe	NonVolatile Memory express
PL	Procedural Language
REST	Representational State Transfer (Fielding 2000)
SQL	Structured Query Language (Codd 1970)
TOML	Tom’s Obvious, Minimal Language
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

Table of Partners

Short Name	Partner
IT4I@VSB	IT4Innovations at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (IT4Innovations) https://www.it4i.cz/en
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities https://www.lrz.de/english/
METU	Middle East Technical University (METU) https://www.metu.edu.tr/
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab https://www.australo.org/
EURAXENT	Euraxent https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraxent/
CVUT	Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics at the Czech Technical University (CIIRC CTU) https://www.ciirc.cvut.cz/
VALEO	Valeo https://www.valeo.com/en/czech-republic/
TERRAVIEW	Terraview https://www.terraview.co/
ALTRNATIV	Altrnativ https://altrnativ.com/?lang=en
VALEO.AI	Valeo.ai https://www.valeo.com/en/valeo-ai/

Executive Summary

The Automated Data Mining System for Systematic Improvement of Molecular Simulations System (ADAMS4SIMS) aims to provide a solution for storing large amounts of Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations and to provide tools for easy, efficient and fast data mining operations. One particular challenge in this is extracting only a small subset of an extreme amount of data needed for relevant analysis across many simulations. The intermediate version of ADAMS4SIMS we present here successfully implements an architecture integrating a web-based GUI, PostgreSQL database, and HDF5 file storage. The system efficiently handles large datasets, with the HDF5 format improving data access speed and storage efficiency.

Preprocessing tools for metadata extraction and data curation, alongside a database schema supporting complex relationships between simulations, molecules, and analytical results have been developed. Initial analysis capabilities, mirroring functionalities of established tools like CPPTRAJ (Roe and Cheatham III 2013), have been integrated. The web-based interface allows for data upload, metadata management, and analysis initiation, while a comprehensive API enables programmatic access for future expansions.

This deliverable presents an important product related to three tasks within WP4 of EXA4MIND: Task 4.2 "Server-side Raw Data Collection and Curation," which includes the provisional implementation of the raw database predicated on the EXA4MIND Extreme Data Database; Task 4.3 "Automated Data Mining"; and Task 4.4 "Client Interface." The work demonstrates significant cross-work-package collaboration:

- ◆ **WP1 (Architecture Co-design):** Close collaboration ensured alignment of ADAMS4SIMS architecture with the overall EXA4MIND architecture, resulting in an integrated system design supporting project goals.
- ◆ **WP2 (Distributed Data Space Management):** WP2 provided expertise in data management strategies, particularly in benchmarking HDF5 format access and exploring alternative storage solutions.
- ◆ **WP3 (Extreme Data Analytics and Processing):** WP3 collaborated on developing preprocessing tools crucial for processing raw simulation data. Integration of the Advanced Query and Indexing System (AQIS) into the system architecture is planned for future development.

ADAMS4SIMS lays a solid foundation for enhancing MD simulation data management and analysis, positioning the project well to achieve its goal of systematically improving molecular simulations through automated data mining techniques.

1 State of the Art

The current state of the art in biomolecular simulation data management is characterised by a diverse ecosystem of repositories, each serving specific facets of the field. General-purpose repositories like Zenodo (European Organization For Nuclear Research and OpenAIRE 2013) and FigShare (FigShare 2024) provide research data management platforms for a broad range of data types, while specialised repositories such as GPCR (Rodríguez-Espigares et al. 2020), MoDEL (Meyer et al. 2010), and BIGNASim (Hospital et al. 2016) cater to niche areas like GPCR protein simulations and MD simulations of DNA molecules, respectively.

Recent initiatives have emphasised the importance of FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016), ensuring that biomolecular simulation data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Discipline-specific databases like BioExcel COVID-19 (Beltrán et al. 2023) and MemProtMD database (Newport, Sansom, and Stansfeld 2018) offer precalculated data and visualization tools, streamlining the research process for scientists worldwide. The recent European initiative MD-DATA ¹ is a notable addition, aiming to unify molecular dynamics repositories for enhanced sharing and sustainability.

The ADAMS4SIMS system contributes to this landscape by focusing on efficient storage, reusability and integration of datasets from different kinds of MD simulations with experimental data. ADAMS4SIMS system is also housing preprocessing and analysis tools that support future force field development, aligning with the community's move towards standardised data management practices. As the field advances, ADAMS4SIMS will continue to integrate with these resources, reinforcing its role in the progression of molecular dynamics simulation research.

2 ADAMS4SIMS Architecture

In collaboration with WP1, we have created our current architecture of the ADAMS4SIMS system that corresponds to the overall EXA4MIND architecture (see Deliverable D1.2 – EXA4MIND 2024a), mapping queries and interface logic to the AQIS system, using the preprocessing toolbox for preprocessing tasks, and leveraging high performance computing (HPC) resources for our preprocessing and analysis workflows. The **ADAMS4SIMS system architecture** is structured to support a comprehensive range of data systems and storage solutions. The current implementation is illustrated in Figure 1, offering an in-depth view of the system's configuration.

Users engage with ADAMS4SIMS through a **web interface** or, for specific operations such as local preprocessing and upload of files, an **alternative CLI interface**. Initially, data are uploaded in their native format to a **raw data storage**, serving both as a backup and a crucial step in the preprocessing workflow facilitated by LEXIS Platform (Golasowski et al. 2022). This preprocessing stage is pivotal for extracting vital metadata and reformatting trajectory data, which are subsequently stored in a **PostgreSQL database** (Stonebraker and Rowe 1986) and **HDF5 format** (Folk et al. 2011),

¹MDDDB project: <https://mddbr.eu>

Figure 1: Architecture of ADAMS4SIMS System.

respectively. In the ADAMS4SIMS architecture, the **query translation** and the **REST API**, are submodules of the AQIS. Details of the initial design of AQIS, with a full architectural view, are given in deliverable D3.1 (EXA4MIND 2024b). The REST API is part of the AQIS Interface submodule. The query transformer, part of the AQIS Query Inference submodule, enables access to storage endpoints through queries expressed

either in database query language or in natural language.

The **Python back-end layer** plays a key role in facilitating user interaction with the data repository, enabling complex analyses and data queries. The integration of **HPC resources** into the system architecture significantly boosts the speed and efficiency of processing.

3 Preprocessing Tools

The ADAMS4SIMS system employs a suite of preprocessing tools essential for managing and processing simulation data, experimental data, and force field data. Preprocessing tools were developed with WP3 as a part of the preprocessing toolbox. The primary focus of these tools is on simulation data, mainly trajectory and topology files, due to its complexity and significance in the project's current phase.

3.1 Data Acquisition and Management

Here, we briefly lay out the methods and processes involved in ingesting and initially managing simulation data within the ADAMS4SIMS system.

Data Ingestion and Storage:

- ◆ Simulation data are ingested using MDAnalysis (Michaud-Agrawal et al. 2011), with an option to load data into memory for expedited processing.
- ◆ Additional files like log and plumed files are supported but not mandatory inputs for every simulation.
- ◆ A configuration TOML file is essential for database connection and preprocessing operations.

User Input and Validation:

- ◆ Users are required to provide specific details that are not retrievable from the simulation files.
- ◆ The system validates file existence and database connectivity before proceeding.
- ◆ All metadata entries are modifiable post-upload to correct processing errors (see Figure 2).

3.2 Metadata Extraction and Database Integration

This subsection explains prerequisites and steps for extracting metadata from simulation files and for integrating data and metadata into our data-storage and database structure.

placeholder_sim_name	2021-04-22 12:13:42
simulation_upload_timestamp:	2024-04-17T11:41:46.676350
simulation_description:	placeholder_simulation_description
sim_name:	placeholder_sim_name
solvent:	
ion_type:	K+Cl-
n_snapshots:	200071
stripped_values:	
time_step:	0.004
total_simulation_time:	1000000
thermostat:	1
barostat:	placeholder_barostat
ladder:	
restraint_file:	placeholder_restraint_file
molecule_id:	<input type="text" value="39"/>
ensemble:	placeholder_ensemble
temperature:	298.16
pressure:	1

Figure 2: Simulation Details View, Modifiable Post-upload.

Metadata processing and database integration:

- ◆ Data classes mirror database tables, facilitating structured data handling.
- ◆ Every data class parameter has either a method for metadata extraction or user metadata insertion.
- ◆ Metadata extraction begins with molecules, followed by simulations, atoms, and paths.
- ◆ Comprehensive extraction is done from trajectory, topology, and additional simulation outputs.
- ◆ Unique IDs are assigned using a PostgreSQL sequence, linking related tables.

Data Storage Formats:

- ◆ Trajectory data are transposed² and stored either in a geometry format³ for databases or directly into HDF5 files.
- ◆ Additional supporting small files, like plumed files⁴, experimental data and others are saved in a PostgreSQL database.
- ◆ HDF5 is preferred for its speed, with the geometry format being phased out.
- ◆ Data are batched into chunks to manage memory usage and processing time.

3.3 Data Insertion Techniques

The following formats and corresponding techniques play a role in our approach for inserting large volumes of data into our data store efficiently:

Geometry Format - Coordinates are batched into CSV files to optimise system memory usage and simplify the database insertion process. Using COPY SQL commands accelerates this approach, because COPY is optimised for loading a large number of rows. It is less flexible than INSERT, but incurs significantly less overhead for large data loads.⁵

HDF5 Format - HDF5 files are generated with predefined sizes to increase insertion speed and minimise the need for dynamic memory allocation.

²Originally the data are stored as one frame with all atoms and their coordinates at one time. Transposed means that they are stored as time series for each atom.

³Trajectory data are coordinates, which can be converted to a line. It thus creates a linestring for one atom. We can understand this line as the evolution of the atom over time. For further information see: <https://postgis.net/workshops/postgis-intro/geometries.html>

⁴Plumed files: <https://www.plumed.org/>

⁵cf. PostgreSQL documentation: <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/current/sql-copy.html>

3.4 Running it: User Interface Driven Preprocessing

Users can interact with the preprocessing tools through our web interface, detailing the workflow from data upload to preprocessing execution. They upload the data through a web interface, where they have to supply mandatory basic metadata. Then, they activate a preprocessing workflow post-upload to execute preprocessing via the LEXIS Platform on an HPC system.

4 Metadata and Data Database

In this section, we explore the structure and implementation of our database system, covering both metadata and raw data storage approaches. In other words, we describe the central data-backend logic behind ADAMS4SIMS system.

4.1 Database ER Diagram

Figure 3 shows a database diagram with mutual relationships. This diagram is a preliminary design that may undergo further changes according to benchmark test results and evolving requirements.

The core of the database consists of a simulation table with relation to a molecule table. The simulation table contains individual paths (simulation runs or simulation replica). Individual paths have coordinate data stored in a HDF5 file. The HDF5 file is made up of time series with coordinates of individual atoms (transposed data – footnote 2, Page 14) as datasets and individual paths as groups. This allows all coordinate data to be stored in one single HDF5 file.

Another set of tables are dedicated to analysis and reweighting. The analyses are stored as an array of values corresponding to atoms for a given type of parameter (distance, dihedral, radial, etc.). Reweighting data contains information about the given force field and their weights.

The force field table (ff) is related to path table and reweighting table. Experimental data are related just to molecule table, because it is possible to compare different experimental data with different simulations, but only for the same molecule.

4.2 Implementation with PostgreSQL Database

For testing and the first version of the system, a Virtual Machine was deployed within the LEXIS OpenStack platform. It has 1.3TB of NVMe storage, and runs PostgreSQL 16.3 on RockyLinux8.

The PostgreSQL database is served by a Python back-end application. It takes care of creating (see Appendix A), importing, extracting and analyzing data. As part of our benchmarking efforts, various data storage approaches were tested. JSON was considered, but it turned out to be insufficient, in terms of the small capacity of the data type (255MB per row). As the second approach, the geometry data format was chosen, storing coordinates in time series as a Linestring (MultiLinestring). However, the time to extract two time series of atoms proved to be insufficient when scaling

Figure 3: Database Schema of the ADAMS4SIMS Database.

the data. HDF5, as a format often used in HPC and storing numbers without ASCII encoding overhead (as in JSON), then prove obviously superior. It achieves excellent results (hundreds of milliseconds) with a certain storage scheme further described in Section 4.1.

5 Data Mining

This section focuses on the analytical capabilities of ADAMS4SIMS system, detailing the implementation of various analysis methods and how users can interact with these tools.

5.1 Implementation of Analysis Methods

We have developed functions (PL/SQL and Python) that mimic the behaviour of the CPPTRAJ software traditionally used in the evaluation of MD simulations. It means we have created functions that calculate user-specified analyses from the data just as the CPPTRAJ software would do, as listed in the following:

- ◆ **get_atoms_coords:** The function returns the coordinates of the specified atoms, for a given simulation and path. For distance, exactly two atoms are required, for dihedral it is exactly 4 atoms.
- ◆ **get_atoms_dist_array:** The function returns a distance for specified 2 atoms in simulation path. Distances are returned in single row as an array. Working with the function **get_atoms_coords** with 2 atoms.
- ◆ **get_distances_for_ptraj:** The function stores a bunch of distances specified within an input table. The input table has data from the user, who specifies which distances must be computed. Working with **get_atoms_dist_array** function with 2 atoms.
- ◆ **compute_torsion_array:** The function returns a dihedral angle for 4 specified atoms in a simulation path. Dihedrals are returned in single row as an array. Working with the **get_atoms_coords** function with 4 atoms.
- ◆ **get_dihedrals_for_ptraj:** The function stores a bunch of dihedrals specified within an input table. The input table has data from a user, who specifies which dihedrals must be computed. Working with the **compute_torsion_array** function with 4 atoms.

5.2 Analysis through User Interface

Users can execute an analysis for a selected simulation by selecting atoms from a simulation and a function/method that should be computed, as can be seen in Figure 4. Included are buttons for analysis row duplication and deletion. This request is then sent to our back-end layer in JSON format, where it is split into separate analysis calls and computed. The results are then saved to a CSV file.

In the current intermediate version, the publicly available features have been strategically limited due to the competitive nature of the field. The web interface focuses on providing pre-analysed data for specific RNA systems, which are crucial for force field development. The current publicly accessible version of ADAMS4SIMS system offers the following features:

- ◆ Pre-analysed data for specific RNA systems, including:
 - ◆ short single-stranded sequences,
 - ◆ suplexes, and
 - ◆ stem-loop motifs.

Figure 4: Analysis Interface.

- ◆ A collection of experimental datasets for these RNA motifs,
- ◆ Sets of predicted signals from MD simulations using common RNA force fields,
- ◆ Tools for comparing the performance of various force fields across different RNA motifs.

The users can explore the overall performance of various force fields and determine which force field performs best for each different RNA motif. This focused approach allows researchers to gain valuable insights into force field accuracy for these crucial RNA structures, for which experimental NMR data is available. We have launched a dedicated webpage containing the current public version of the ADAMS4SIMS web interface at <https://ida.4sims.eu>.

6 Back-end Service Layer

The back-end service layer is the cornerstone of the ADAMS4SIMS system, facilitating user interaction with the database and the execution of complex data analyses. It encompasses the API interface, intermediate data representation, and the core analysis logic.

6.1 API Implementation

ADAMS4SIMS API endpoints (see Figure 5) have been designed to provide users with comprehensive access and control over the simulation data. These endpoints implement the following functionality:

FastAPI 0.1.0 OAS 3.1
/openapi.json

default ^

GET	/simulations	Simulations	∨
GET	/simulations/{simulation_id}/atoms	Get Atoms For Simulation	∨
PUT	/simulations/{simulation_id}	Simulations	∨
GET	/force_fields	Force Fields	∨
GET	/experimental_data	Experimental Data	∨
POST	/analysis	Analysis	∨

Figure 5: ADAMS4SIMS API Endpoints.

- ◆ **Viewing Simulations:** Users can retrieve a list of all simulations, complete with their metadata, to quickly identify and select relevant datasets for further analysis.
- ◆ **Metadata Management:** The API enables users to view detailed metadata for each simulation and, if necessary, update this information to reflect changes in data interpretation or simulation parameters.
- ◆ **Analysis Execution:** Users can initiate predefined analysis tasks on selected simulations. The API handles the task queuing and execution, returning results as a CSV file.

6.2 Intermediate Data Representation

This representation abstracts the raw data into a structured format that is optimised for analysis. It converts raw simulation data into NumPy (Harris et al. 2020) arrays that are more conducive to analysis, ensuring that computational operations are efficient and scalable.

6.3 Analysis Logic

Our build-in analysis core logic incorporates a suite of data mining algorithms tailored to MD simulations, capable of identifying patterns and correlations within the data. These currently include calculations for distances and dihedrals. The users are able to define custom analysis scripts based on their selection through our web interface, described in Section 5.2. These calculations are then passed through our analysis pipeline, which is designed to efficiently handle large datasets, leveraging the speed of NumPy for numerical computations and the HDF5 format for data retrieval.

7 Code and Documentation

The codebase for the ADAMS4SIMS system is documented and maintained, ensuring that all developments are accessible and comprehensible to both current project members and future internal or external contributors.

7.1 Preprocessing Code

The preprocessing code is a crucial component of the ADAMS4SIMS system, responsible for preparing simulation data for analysis. It is available at the IT4I@VSB OpenCode GitLab platform (<https://opencode.it4i.eu>) hosting the EXA4MIND codebase.

7.2 Back-end Code

The back-end code, which includes the API implementations and analysis logic, is maintained on the IT4I@VSB OpenCode Gitlab as well. This repository contains:

- ◆ **API Code:** The implementation of the APIs that facilitate user interaction with the simulation data.
- ◆ **Analysis Logic:** The algorithms and computational logic required to perform data mining on the simulation data.

7.3 Front-end Code

The front-end code, which implements the user interface and client-side logic of ADAMS4SIMS, is maintained as a separate branch within our main repository on the IT4I@VSB OpenCode Gitlab. This approach allows for integrated version control while keeping the front-end and back-end codebases distinct. The front-end is built using React.js, a popular JavaScript library for building user interfaces (cf. e.g. Fedosejev 2015). We utilise additional libraries (cf. e.g. Satoshi Yoshida and Simona Yoshida 2021) such as the Redux Toolkit for state management and RTK Query for handling HTTP requests.

7.4 Documentation Standards

Both the preprocessing and back-end codes are documented according to the following standards:

- ◆ **Code Comments:** Inline comments explain the functionality of complex code blocks and algorithms.
- ◆ **API Documentation:** Detailed descriptions of API endpoints, parameters, and expected responses are provided.

- ◆ **README files:** Comprehensive README files are curated, with instructions for environment setup and example code executions with examples.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined the progress made in the development of the ADAMS4SIMS system, a robust system designed to enhance the management and analysis of biomolecular simulation data. Through the implementation of a user-friendly web interface, ADAMS4SIMS provides researchers the tools necessary to upload, preprocess, and analyse large datasets efficiently.

Looking ahead, the next steps for the ADAMS4SIMS system include:

- ◆ **Enhancing Data Accessibility:** Continuing efforts to align with FAIR principles, ensuring that all data processed by ADAMS4SIMS are easily accessible and reusable by the scientific community.
- ◆ **Developing Advanced Analysis Tools:** Creating more sophisticated tools for data analysis, expanding our array of available tools, to provide deeper insights into simulation data.
- ◆ **Community Engagement:** Engaging with the user community to gather feedback, identify areas for improvement, and incorporate new features that address the evolving needs of researchers.
- ◆ **Implement User Roles:** Accommodating different user needs and abilities, and assigning users appropriate roles to access to different parts of the system accordingly.
- ◆ **Force Field Development:** Focusing on the support for future force field development to ensure that ADAMS4SIMS remains at the forefront of simulation data analysis.

As the project moves forward, ADAMS4SIMS system will continue to adapt and evolve in collaboration with the technical EXA4MIND work packages, ensuring that the system meets the highest standards of data management and contributes to the advancement of scientific research.

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Appendices

A Create SQL statements

```
CREATE SCHEMA "sim";

CREATE TABLE "sim"."simulation" (
  "id" serial PRIMARY KEY,
  "doi" text,
  "author_name" varchar,
  "upload_user_id" bigint,
  "software_name" varchar,
  "software_settings" varchar,
  "software_version" varchar,
  "creation_timestamp" timestamp,
  "upload_timestamp" timestamp,
  "simulation_description" text,
  "sim_name" varchar,
  "solvent" text[],
  "ion_type" text[],
  "ionic_concentration" float,
  "num_snapshots" integer,
  "stripping_mask" text,
  "ensemble_parameter_type" text,
  "time_step" float,
  "total_sim_time" float,
  "thermostat" text,
  "barostat" text,
  "ensemble_ladder" text[],
  "restraint_file" bytea,
  "molecule_id" int,
  "ensemble" text,
  "temperature" float,
  "pressure" float
);

CREATE TABLE "sim"."path" (
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,
  "run_name" varchar,
  "type" varchar,
  "box_initial" numeric[],
  "box_change" boolean,
  "box_final" numeric[],
  "following_parametr" varchar,
  "following_value" varchar,
  "simulation_id" integer,
  "plumed" bytea,
  "ff_id" bigint,
  "hdf5_file_id" bigint
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE "sim"."hdf5_files" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "simulation_id" bigint,  
  "rel_path" text,  
  "folder" text  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."molecule" (  
  "id" serial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "sequence" text,  
  "type" text[],  
  "organism" text,  
  "organism_description" text,  
  "upload_timestamp" timestamp,  
  "upload_user_id" bigint  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."ff" (  
  "id" serial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "doi" text,  
  "ff_name" text,  
  "molecule_type" text[],  
  "ff_library_file" bytea,  
  "ff_parm_file" bytea,  
  "ff_leaprc_file" bytea,  
  "definition" text,  
  "data_publication_time" timestamp,  
  "data_upload_time" timestamp,  
  "reference_article_doi" text,  
  "author_name" text,  
  "upload_user_id" bigint  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."sim_ff" (  
  "simulation_id" bigint,  
  "ff_id" int  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."experimental_data" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "doi" text,  
  "molecule_id" bigint,  
  "exp_data_type" text,  
  "values" bytea,  
  "data_publication_time" timestamp,  
  "data_upload_time" timestamp,  
  "reference_article_doi" text,  
  "author_name" text,  
  "upload_user_id" bigint,  
  "temperature" float  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE "sim"."comparison_with_experimental_data" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "simulation_id" bigint,  
  "ff_id" bigint,  
  "value" float,  
  "significane" float  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."input_analysis" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "path_id" bigint,  
  "upload_user_id" bigint,  
  "parametr_type" text,  
  "atoms" text[]  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."analysis" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "path_id" bigint,  
  "upload_user_id" bigint,  
  "parametr_type" text,  
  "atoms_order_id" int[],  
  "values" float[],  
  "reweighting_id" bigint  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."path_based_analysis" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "analysis_id" bigint,  
  "path_id" bigint,  
  "description" text,  
  "computed_values" numeric[]  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."reweighting" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "ff_id" bigint  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."path_based_reweighting" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "reweighting_id" bigint,  
  "path_id" bigint,  
  "weight" float  
);  
  
CREATE TABLE "sim"."user" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "username" text,  
  "authorization" text  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE "sim"."atom" (  
  "id" bigserial PRIMARY KEY,  
  "order_id" int,  
  "simulation_id" bigint,  
  "atom_name" text,  
  "res_name" text,  
  "conc_name" text  
);
```